

1 *Review*

2 **Olive Mill Wastes: a source of bioactive molecules for** 3 **plant growth and protection against pathogens**

4 **Fabio Sciubba^{1,2§}, Laura Chronopoulou^{1§}, Daniele Pizzichini^{3§}, Vincenzo Lionetti⁴, Claudia**
5 **Fontana⁵, Rita Aromolo⁵, Silvia Socciarelli⁵, Loretta Gambelli⁶, Barbara Bartolacci⁷, Enrico**
6 **Finotti⁶, Anna Benedetti⁵, Alfredo Miccheli^{2,8,9}, Ulderico Neri⁵, Cleofe Palocci^{1,9*} and Daniela**
7 **Bellincampi^{4,9*}**

8 § equally contributing authors

9 ¹ Department of Chemistry, Sapienza University of Rome, 00185 Rome, Italy; FS

10 fabio.sciubba@uniroma1.it, LC laura.chronopoulou@uniroma1.it, CP cleofe.palocci@uniroma1.it

11 ² NMR-based Metabolomics Laboratory, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, 00185, Italy; FS

12 fabio.sciubba@uniroma1.it, AM alfredo.miccheli@uniroma1.it

13 ³ Bio-products-Bio-processes laboratory, division of biotechnology and agriculture, Department for
14 Sustainability. ENEA, Casaccia Research Center, 00123 Rome, Italy; DP daniele.pizzichini@enea.it

15 ⁴ Department of Biology and Biotechnology Charles Darwin, Sapienza University of Rome, 00185 Rome,
16 Italy; VL vincenzo.lionetti@uniroma1.it, DB daniela.bellincampi@uniroma1.it

17 ⁵ CREA-Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Centre for Agriculture and
18 Environment, 00184 Rome, Italy; CF claudia.fontana@crea.gov.it, RA rita.aromolo@crea.gov.it, SS

19 silvia.socciarelli@crea.gov.it, AB anna.benedetti@crea.gov.it, UN ulderico.neri@crea.gov.it

20 ⁶ CREA- Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Centre for Food and Nutrition, 00184
21 Rome, Italy; LG loretta.gambelli@crea.gov.it, EF enrico.finotti@crea.gov.it

22 ⁷ Order of Agronomists and Forestry Doctors, Province of Viterbo, 01100 Viterbo, Italy; BB
23 studiobartolacci.agr@gmail.com

24 ⁸ Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, 00185, Italy; AM
25 alfredo.miccheli@uniroma1.it

26 ⁹ CIABC, Sapienza University of Rome, 00185 Rome, Italy; AM alfredo.miccheli@uniroma1.it, CP
27 cleofe.palocci@uniroma1.it, DB daniela.bellincampi@uniroma1.it;

28 * Correspondence: DB daniela.bellincampi@uniroma1.it; CP cleofe.palocci@uniroma1.it

29 Received: date; Accepted: date; Published: date

30 **Simple Summary:** Olive oil is the most common vegetable oil used for human nutrition, and its
31 production represents a major economic sector in Mediterranean countries. The milling industry
32 generates large amounts of liquid and solid residues, whose disposal is complicated and costly
33 because of their polluting properties. However, olive mill waste (OMW) may be also seen as a source
34 of valuable biomolecules including plant nutrients, anthocyanins, flavonoids, polysaccharides and
35 phenolic compounds. This review describes recent advances and multidisciplinary approaches in
36 the identification and isolation of valuable natural OMW-derived bioactive molecules. Such natural
37 compounds may be potentially used in numerous sustainable applications in agriculture such as
38 fertilizers, biostimulants, biopesticides in alternative to synthetic substances that have a negative
39 impact on the environment and are harmful to human health.

40

41 **Abstract:** Olive oil production generates high amounts of liquid and solid wastes. For a long time,
42 such complex matrices were considered only as an environmental issue, because of their polluting
43 properties. On the other hand, olive mill wastes (OMW) exert positive effect on plant growth when
44 applied to soil due to the high content of organic matter and mineral nutrients. Moreover, OMW
45 also exhibit antimicrobial activity and protective properties against plant pathogens possibly due to

46 the presence of bioactive molecules including phenols and polysaccharides. This review covers the
47 recent advances made in the identification, isolation and characterization of OMW-derived
48 bioactive molecules able to influence important plant processes such as plant growth and defense
49 against pathogens. Such studies are relevant from different points of view. Firstly, basic research in
50 plant biology may benefit from the isolation and characterization of new biomolecules to be
51 potentially applied in crop growth and protection against diseases. Moreover, the valorization of
52 waste materials is necessary for the development of circular economy that is foreseen to drive the
53 future development of a more sustainable agriculture.

54

55 **Keywords:** *Olea europaea* L., Olive mill wastes; plant growth; plant nutrition; plant protection;
56 phenols; oligosaccharides; bioactive molecules

57 1. Introduction

58 Olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.) cultivation for olive oil production is one the most ancient
59 agricultural practices known by mankind. Olive oil is an important component of the Mediterranean
60 diet known for its high nutritional properties and beneficial health effects. On average, 3 million tons
61 of olive oil are produced around the world every year and 2 million tons of this production takes
62 place in the European Union (EU) representing the first producer, exporter and consumer of olive oil
63 in the world. The Mediterranean area alone including Spain, Italy, Greece and Portugal covers
64 around 99% of the olive oil EU production [1].

65 Olive oil extraction includes washing of olive fruits, fruit crushing, malaxation to brake off the
66 emulsion and facilitate coalescence and finally oil separation and extraction.

67 Olive oil extraction processes have improved over time due to the intensification of oil
68 production and to the modernization of the technology aimed to upgrade the quality of the final
69 product.

70 The milling industry generates in a short period, usually of four months (October-January), large
71 amounts of waste (olive mill waste, OMW). For instance, an estimated average volume of olive mill
72 wastewater (OMWW) ranging from about 0.3 to 1.2 m³ /tons of processed olives and an average
73 quantity of solid residue ranging from 500 to 735 kg /tons of processed olives have been reported
74 depending on extraction systems adopted [2]. OMWs due to their acidity, high levels of Biological
75 Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) are characterized by a high polluting
76 and phytotoxic degree [3]. On the other hand, OMWs are a source of valuable molecules including
77 plant nutrients, anthocyanins, flavonoids, polysaccharides and several phenolic compounds [4–6]
78 with potential industrial applications as fertilizers, antioxidants, antifungal and antibacterial drugs,
79 cytoprotective agents, gelling and stabilizing agents in food preservation [4,7]. Consequently,
80 significant efforts have been devoted to the transition from OMW detoxification to its valorization by
81 optimizing the recovery of high added-value bioactive compounds to be commercially reused.

82 The increasing consumption of vegetables and the ongoing climate changes, with negative
83 effects on crop production and plant diseases diffusion, requires the large utilization of stimulants,
84 fertilizers and pesticides to improve plant growth, crop yield and phytopathogens control [8]. The
85 future challenge for modern agriculture is to operate in a sustainable way reducing the over-
86 application of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides that have a negative impact on the environment and
87 on human health and high persistence in the ecosystems. As alternative to synthetic chemicals,
88 biostimulants and biopesticides are the best candidates for sustainable integrated crop productivity
89 and pest management [9,10]. Bioactive molecules with growth promotion and antimicrobial effects,
90 identified and characterized in OMW by-products, have stimulated many researchers to employ
91 these compounds as biostimulants, biopesticides and plant protectants for crop improvement.
92 However, more extensive field research is required to evaluate their effects to solve serious plant
93 diseases affecting commercially important crops with sustainable large-scale agro-economical
94 perspective.

95 This review summarizes recent advances and multidisciplinary approaches in the identification
96 and possible agronomic exploitation of valuable natural OMW-derived bioactive compounds. The
97 acquired knowledge could also lead to the discovery of new plant growth and disease resistance
98 regulators.

99 2. Olive oil extractive methods and Olive mill wastes

100 From the classic traditional discontinuous system, modern mills have moved to the use of
101 continuous cycle extraction processes including two-, three-phase decanter systems [3] and, more
102 recently, multi-phase decanter (MPD) technology in which all the oil extraction steps take place
103 automatically and in succession with higher efficiency and capacity of centrifuge-based extraction
104 [11].

105 In the three-phase decanter system warm water, up to 50 L for 100 kg olive paste, is added during
106 malaxation to enhance oil extraction. At the end of the process, a large quantity of OMWWs (0.3 – 1.2
107 m³ / tons of processed olives) and Dried Olive Pomace (DOP) (about 580 kg / tons of processed olives;
108 55% moisture) are produced [2].

109 The two-phase decanter system requires lower water addition, thus smaller amounts of
110 OMWWs (about 0.2-0.3 m³ / tons of processed olives) are generated and a semi-solid waste, defined
111 Wet Olive Pomace (WOP) (about 740 kg / tons of processed olive; 62% moisture) is produced [2].
112 WOP treatment is difficult due to the high moisture and high concentration in solids, lipids,
113 carbohydrates and polyphenols [12].

114 MPD technology is a modern two-phase system performed without adding water during the
115 process. The introduction of a pulp-kernel separation system produces a dehydrated kernel-enriched
116 fraction and a novel by-product, named Patè Olive Cake (POC) recovered during and not after the
117 milling process by an exclusively mechanical treatment. POC consists of a wet fraction composed by
118 olive pulp, olive skin and vegetative water. POC is rich in several bioactive molecules, more
119 concentrated with respect to OP derived from three or two phase systems [13–16].

120 OMWW is an expensive waste to dispose of and a major environmental concern in olive
121 producing countries due to its high pollutant charge. OMWW is a dark-brown liquid (pH 3-6),
122 constituted by a stable emulsion of vegetative water, process water, olive oil residues and fragments
123 of olive pulp. OMWW composition depends on the extraction system, processed fruits and
124 processing conditions. OMWW consists of water (83–94% w/w) and organic compounds (4–18%
125 w/w) including sugars, polysaccharides, tannins, organic acids, phenolic compounds and lipids [17].
126 Its great complexity and variability in chemical composition represents a limit to its direct use as a
127 raw material for industrial purposes.

128 3. Active molecules in OMW and their analytical characterization

129 In order to valorize wastes and introduce valuable by-products into the production cycle, it is of
130 paramount importance to define their chemical-physical properties as well as their chemical
131 composition. For a long time, the most important parameters to define wastes were the chemical-
132 physical ones, such as total solid, volatile solid, fixed solid, oil and grease content, polyphenol
133 content, volatile phenol content, organic nitrogen, COD and reducing sugar content.

134 More recently, analytical platforms were employed to better characterize the OMW parameters
135 and a greater emphasis was placed on the evaluation of the antioxidant properties of these matrices
136 [18,19].

137 The most used methods in order to detect the antioxidant capacity of single or multiple
138 molecules, are oxygen radical absorbance capacity [20], total radical trapping antioxidant parameter
139 [21], Ferric reducing antioxidant power [22], antioxidant reaction with an organic cation radical [23]
140 (diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) copper (II) reduction capacity [24] and crocin bleaching assay [25,26].

141 The natural evolution of such studies is the investigation of the composition of OMW in terms
142 of phenols, polyphenols and sugars with more powerful techniques such as Fourier Transform IR,
143 Mass Spectroscopy, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy or a combination of these [4,18,27–
144 33] (see Table 1).

145 The content of bioactive molecules in OMW is heavily influenced by agronomic factors, such as
 146 pedoclimatic conditions of olive groves as well as olive variety, harvest period, production year and
 147 extraction process as well as microbial treatments [6,34,35]. This observation implies that the chemical
 148 characterization of OMW is a step which must be repeated every time that a new batch is to be
 149 employed for any kind of application [36].

150 Only recently POC is being considered for other uses beside biofuel production [16,37], and as
 151 such a more detailed biochemical analysis is necessary. HPLC chromatography and Gas Mass
 152 spectroscopy could be fast and economical methods to detect phenols [38] while hyphenated
 153 platforms like Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography coupled with a mass spectrometry
 154 detector without pre-treatment of sample [39] can provide greater selectivity and sensitivity. A
 155 summary of the most recent studies concerning the bioactive molecules of OMW is reported in Table
 156 1, and some of the most important molecules and their properties are briefly introduced in the
 157 following paragraphs.
 158

159 **Table 1.** Recent studies on the characterization of bioactive phenolic compounds in OMWs.

Molecule	Analytical platform	Amount in OMWW (mg/g dry matter)	OMWW References	Amount in POC (mg/g dry matter)	POC References
Phenols					
Tyrosol	HPLC, MS, GC, NMR	1.0-2.8	[6,40–44]	0.4-1	[13,15,16,45]
Hydroxytyrosol	HPLC, MS, GC, NMR	0.9-24	[6,40–44]	0.6-2	[13,15,16,45]
Hydroxybenzoic acid	HPLC, MS, GC, NMR	2-9	[6,40,43]	/	/
Coumaric acid	HPLC, MS, GC, NMR	1-2	[40,43]	0.1-0.6	[13,16]
Gallic acid	HPLC, MS	2-6	[6,40]	/	/
Vanillic acid	HPLC, MS	0.1-0.6	[6,40]	0.5-0.8	[16]
Caffeic acid	HPLC, MS	0.3-1.9	[6,40]	0.9-5.0	[13,15,45]
Hydroxycinnamic acid	HPLC, MS	Detected	[42]	/	/
Polyphenols					
Quercetin-3-O-glucoside	HPLC, MS	0.5-2.1	[40,44]	/	/
Luteolin-7-O-glucosides	HPLC, MS	25-55	[6,41,44]	0.5-1.2	[13,15]
Secoiridoids					
Oleuropein	HPLC, MS, GC	18-92	[6,40–42,44]	0.1-9.2	[15,16,45]
Oleuropein aglycone	HPLC, MS	Detected	[41]	Detected	[45]
Ligstroside	HPLC, MS	Detected	[41]	/	/
Ligstroside aglycone	HPLC, MS	Detected	[41]	/	/
Oleacantal	HPLC, MS	Detected	[41,44]	0.1-0.4	[13]

160

161 *3.1. Phenols and Polyphenols*

162 Phenolics in plants are mainly synthesized through the phenylpropanoid pathway. Several
163 phenols and polyphenols have been detected in OMWs (e.g. 32.8-103.4 mg/g dry matter in OMWW
164 and 3.0-10.6 mg/g dry matter in POC, see Table 1), the most important ones being tyrosol,
165 hydroxytyrosol and their secoiridoid derivatives oleuropein and ligstroside. These compounds play
166 an important role against inflammatory, aging, cancer, bacterial and other diseases [46]. From a
167 technological point of view, hydroxytyrosol could be very useful, but its synthesis is very expensive
168 and it is not commercially available in large amounts [47]. For such reasons, the possibility to recover
169 these compounds from natural matrices such as OMW could be an important goal.

170 3.2. Secoiridoids

171 The most diffused secoiridoids in OMW (e.g. 18-91 mg/g dry matter in OMWW and 0.2-9.6 mg/g
172 dry matter in POC, see Table 1) are derived from elenolic acid, which is often esterified with
173 hydroxytyrosol or tyrosol to form the aglycons of, respectively, oleuropein and ligstroside [29,48–51].
174 Other common derivatives are based on decarboxymethyl dialdehyde elenolic acid (oleacein) instead
175 of elenolic acid. These molecules possess several properties beside their antioxidant potential with
176 oleuropein, ligstroside and their aglycons showing significant antifungal and antimicrobial activity
177 as well as potential health benefits [52–55].

178 3.3. Carbohydrates

179 Carbohydrates in OMWs are released following cell wall degradation during the milling process
180 and during the olives ripening process. The knowledge of the composition of the cell wall
181 polysaccharides of the olive fruit and of OMWs is useful to evaluate their potential applications [56].
182 Green olives, mostly used for oil production, have a cell wall composed by 46% of pectin
183 polysaccharides (mainly galacturonan and arabinans), 28% Cellulose, 17% Glucuronoxylan, 10%
184 Xyloglucan, 1% Mannan, and Arabinose-Rich Glycoprotein in traces [57,58]. Differences can be
185 revealed between cultivars and ripening stages. Pectin-related sugars (Galacturonic Acid;GalA,
186 Rhamnose;Rha, and Arabinose;Ara) are abundant in olives early during ripening whereas
187 hemicellulose monosaccharides (Xylose;Xyl, Mannose;Man, Galactose;Gal, and Glucose;Glc) increase
188 later during maturation [59,60].

189 Cell wall isolation from OMW typically requires a hot ethanol precipitation followed by an
190 alkali, acid or solvent treatment. The monosaccharide composition is usually performed by HPAEC-
191 PAD or GS-MS analysis associated with several colorimetric assays [60–62]. Differently from the OP,
192 where insoluble cellulose and hemicelluloses are mainly present, OMWW is enriched in soluble
193 pectins [62,63]. Polysaccharides isolated from OMWW are mainly enriched in GalA, followed by Ara,
194 Glc and Gal [62,64]. Conversely, Nadour et al found that Glc was the major monosaccharide in the
195 cell wall from OMWW, followed by Rha, Gal, Ara, Man, Xyl, and GalA. GlcA and fucose (Fuc)
196 appearing as minor sugars [5]. The differences observed among different studies can be explained by
197 the different extraction or analytical methods used, and/or by different varieties or ripening stages of
198 the olives. Evidence suggests that OMW is a source of partially soluble cellooligo-saccharides (COS),
199 pectooligosaccharides (POS), xylooligosaccharides (XOS) [65]. These oligomers compose a class of
200 value-added compounds with enormous potential. All these oligosaccharides play a fundamental
201 role as plant growth promoters or as defenders against pathogens [66–69]. Moreover, cell wall-
202 derived products may have different nutritional and physiological benefits [70,71]. Possibly due to
203 a recent interest in these OMW derived oligosaccharides, a fine characterization of their chemical
204 structure is not yet available in the literature. Such information is essential for designing new paths
205 for the exploitation of OMW and its by-products in agriculture. The presence of glycosylated phenolic
206 acids was also proposed for OMWW [5,72,73].

207 OMW are also enriched in soluble sugars, including significant amounts of Glc and Man and
208 small quantities of Sucrose and Fructose [74]. Mannose can increase tolerance to salt and osmotic
209 stress as 'compatible solute' and can play a role in the responses to pathogen attack as well as being
210 heavily used in the food industry [75,76]. However, caution is required since it can have a negative
211 effect on plant growth and defense when administered to plants in high doses [77]. A polymeric

212 mixture, named polymerin, was also recovered from OMWW. It is composed of polysaccharides
213 (54.4%), melanin (26.1%), protein (10.4%) and minerals (11.06 %) strongly linked through covalent
214 and hydrogen bonds. Polymerin could be used as a potential amendment, and/or metal biointegrator
215 and as biofilter for toxic metals [78,79].

216 4. Sustainable processes for the isolation of bioactive molecules from OMWs

217 Several extraction methodologies for the recovery of OMW-derived bioactive substances are
218 mostly based on the use of organic solvents. However, there is an increasing need for green and
219 sustainable extraction approaches at low environmental impact. Membrane-based techniques such
220 as microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF), and reverse osmosis (RO), constitute
221 one of the most effective approaches to separate, concentrate, and finally recover active compounds
222 [80]. These technologies considered BAT (best available techniques) are characterized by high
223 separation efficiency, easy scale-up, high productivity. These features make cross-flow processes
224 more performing than conventional separation technologies. The effectiveness of MF as pre-
225 treatment for OMWW clarification was investigated in coupling with membrane distillation process.
226 The MF permeate was further treated through a membrane distillation stage, in order to obtain both
227 a clean water and a fraction containing concentrated phenols and sugars for fertilization purposes
228 [81]. With this strategy hydroxytyrosol was the main phenolic substance recovered concentrated to
229 8.16 g/L. UF 50 kDa cut-off was applied to separate the phenolic fraction and to lower COD content
230 of OMWW [82]. Different operating conditions were evaluated in terms of rejection to: COD, color,
231 total solids and total phenolic content. The results indicate the UF in acidic condition is a suitable pre-
232 treatment for OMWW improving phenolic compounds recovery and environmental impact
233 reduction. Different UF and NF membranes were used to separate from OMWW a pectin and a
234 phenol-enriched fraction. Specific UF membranes (25 and 100 kDa cut off) were effective to separate
235 pectins from a mixture of cations and phenols. Finally, NF was utilized to separate phenols from
236 cations in solution [83] making this approach useful to separate different molecules from OMWW.
237 Oligosaccharides fractions (3-1 kDa) were separated from WOP treated in a hydrothermal reactor
238 and subjected to further chemical and enzymatical hydrolysis. UF was applied to separate tetra-, tri-
239 and di-galacturonic acids, neutral and acidic xylo-oligosaccharides and low molecular weight
240 oligosaccharides of xyloglucan [84]. A membrane process based on ceramic UF, polymeric NF and
241 RO, was adopted on water extracts of OP in order to concentrate target compounds. UF concentrate
242 contains polyphenols (550 mg/L) and carbohydrates (4000 mg/L), in comparison NF concentrate
243 shows more polyphenols (652 mg/L), and less carbohydrates (3000 mg/L). RO retains the remaining
244 organic fraction returning a clean permeate with a total COD of 284 mg/L [12].

245 Photocatalysis has been studied as OMW pretreatment to be applied before membrane
246 fractionation. In order to achieve economic feasibility of the process, the catalyst must be recovered
247 but immobilized systems cannot be used due to the high opacity of OMWW. Magnetic core titania
248 particles, recoverable by means of a magnetic trap, were developed [85]. Their use permitted to
249 efficiently perform the pretreatment process of the wastewater stream, by using a suspended
250 photocatalyst photoreactor, recovering up to 98% of the catalyst. By adopting photocatalysis as a
251 pretreatment step for membranes, it was possible to increase process productivity of 19% on average.
252 COD values below 1.3 g/L were measured in the final permeate streams, achieving the quality
253 standards for irrigation.

254 Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is being considered an advantageous eco-sustainable
255 technique for biomass fractionation, starting from solid dehydrated materials [86–88]. Olive leaves
256 have been used as a polyphenols source for SFE. CO₂ modified by water was more efficient than that
257 modified by ethanol in extracting oleuropein from olive leaves [89,90]. Water swells the matrix,
258 opening pores and allowing better access to solutes. Other authors described the use of different
259 waste materials such as pruning biomass, leaves and exhaust pomace as a source of polyphenols [91].
260 For all materials, SFE afforded extracts with a higher concentration of total polyphenols and higher
261 antioxidant activity compared to SE. Hydroxytyrosol was the most prominent detected compound.
262 Schievano et al. proposed an integrated biorefinery concept for the management of pomace, using

263 SFE for extracting polyphenols and fatty acids, followed by thermochemical recovery of energy,
264 biofuels and materials [92].

265 **5. Application of OWS and OMW-derived bioactive molecules in plant growth and protection**

266 *5.1. Effects of OMW as Plant biostimulants*

267 The new EU Regulation 2019/1009 [93] defines a plant biostimulant (PB) as: “an EU fertilizing
268 product the function of which is to stimulate plant nutrition processes independently of the product's
269 nutrient content with the sole aim of improving one or more of the following characteristics of the
270 plant or the plant rhizosphere: i) nutrient use efficiency, ii) tolerance to abiotic stress, iii) quality traits,
271 or iv) availability of confined nutrients in the soil or rhizosphere”.

272 The members of the European Biostimulant Industry Council also proposed general principles
273 and guidelines for trials and assays to be performed to allow PBs to be placed on the EU market [94].
274 In the last 10 years (2011–2020) about 1000 scientific papers were published on PBs and OMWs are
275 recognized as biostimulants, although there is still little specific research on them [95].

276 Palumbo's research [96] indicates that humic acids extracted from an amendment obtained
277 combining OMWs with a pre-treated organic material derived from solid urban waste can be used as
278 PB in agriculture thanks to their positive effects on biomass production, nutrition and activity of
279 enzymes implied in N metabolism and glycolysis. Other studies have shown that PB formed as a by-
280 product of the two-stage process of squeezing olive oil can induce an increase in the protein content
281 of maize grains up to 19% [9]. OMW, at low concentrations, can efficiently trigger positive metabolic
282 and physiological responses in plants [9].

283 Phenols are important signaling molecules and it has been established that in adequate
284 concentrations they can produce several positive effects in plants, even when they are exogenously
285 applied or present in PB formulations [9,97]. Conversely, at concentrations as high as those normally
286 recorded in OMW, phenols may be responsible for inhibition of soil microbiome activity and
287 induction of several phytotoxic effects, including reduced seed germination, plant growth
288 impairment and drops in productivity [98,99].

289 *5.2. Effects of OMW on soil properties and plant nutrition*

290 The effects of land spreading of OMW on soil properties have been investigated and the results
291 show that the effects on soil properties and plant growth are different according to the kind of OMW
292 (liquid or solid, raw or processed). The form and rate in which OMWs are applied to soils play a
293 significant role in determining their effectiveness as organic fertilizers and in soil health [100]. On the
294 other hand, many studies investigated the effects of unprocessed OMWW on soil characteristics,
295 recording negative effects on soil properties [101] and phytotoxic effects in seeds and plants when
296 OMW is used directly as an organic fertilizer [102]. These wastes, due to their acidity, high organic
297 load, high levels of BOD, COD, presence of high and low molecular weight polyphenols, short and
298 long-chain fatty acids and inorganic substances, can be characterized by a high polluting and
299 phytotoxic degree. The reduction of OMW toxicity has been related to the degradation of phenolic
300 compounds considered as the main responsible for the toxic effects on seed germination, on bacteria
301 and on different species of soil and aquatic invertebrates [103]. Nevertheless OMWs characteristics
302 make them suitable for use as low-cost soil fertilizers recycling the organic matter and mineral
303 nutrients [104]; moreover clarified OMWW can represent a convenient source of irrigation water in
304 Mediterranean countries suffering of water scarcity [105–110]. To solve the environmental problems
305 linked to OMW disposal costs and to allow its application to agricultural soils, several physico-
306 chemical and biotechnological processes have been proposed for OMW treatment based on
307 evaporation ponds, reverse osmosis, filtration, oxidation, thermal drying, aerobic and anaerobic
308 treatments, composting, phyto-depuration, phenolic components extraction [111]. The impact on soil
309 properties depends on the techniques used. Treated OMWs have no toxic effects and in general
310 enhance soil fertility and plant growth [107,112,113]. However, technological process application is
311 limited due to the high investment or running cost [114] and the most frequently used ways to

312 dispose of OMW nowadays are the application to agricultural soils of unprocessed OMW or after
313 composting [33,115–119] or co-composting [120–122].

314 From the literature, OMW, solid and liquid, raw or processed forms, may affect soil chemical,
315 physical and biological properties in different ways that, in turn, influence the growth and yield of
316 crops as follows.

317 - **Chemical properties:** The physico-chemical characteristics of raw or processed OMW are
318 adequate for an agronomic use as organic fertilizer such as a slightly acidic pH, a very high content
319 of organic matter and balanced concentrations of mineral elements [123]. An important advantage of
320 OMW is that it is free of heavy metals and other potential pollutants [124]. Many studies reported the
321 general increase of the organic matter, organic N, macro and micronutrients on the soil, in particular
322 available K [104,114,125,126]. Long term application of OMW in general did not cause significant
323 differences in pH, EC, P, Na. However, pH, EC and salinity can increase temporarily in topsoil after
324 spreading high rates (200 m³/(ha*year)) of OMWW [109,110,127–130]

325 - **Physical and hydrological properties:** Different results are reported in function of forms of
326 OMW (solid or liquid), rates of application and pretreatments.

327 Land applications of raw or composted PO increase water retention and saturated hydraulic
328 conductivity, reduce bulk density and enhance the stability of aggregates with improved water
329 availability for the crops. The increase in water holding capacity and wilting point can be attributed
330 to changes in soil structure which result from increases in soil organic Carbon [131–133].

331 However, the accumulation of salts coming from irrigation with OMWW could lead to the
332 disintegration of the soil structure and therefore the decrease of the hydraulic conductivity and a
333 temporary reduction in the soil infiltration rate. In the topsoil, irrigation with OMWW produced an
334 increase of stability of aggregates, lower bulk density and relatively higher total porosity, but lower
335 macroporosity [109,134–136].

336 Further advantages of OMW application is the reduction of erosion, runoff, soil losses [131] and
337 pesticides persistence and mobility, decreasing groundwater risk contamination [137].

338 - **Biological properties:** The high polyphenols content of OMW represents the most limiting
339 factor for spreading on soils because of their antimicrobial and phytotoxic effects. Nevertheless,
340 OMW polyphenols are rapidly degraded depending on environmental conditions [105]. As regards
341 the soil microflora, OMW exercises the following two contrasting actions: it stimulates the
342 development of the microflora by temporarily enriching the soil in carbon and inhibits some
343 microorganisms and phytopathogenic agents due to the presence of antimicrobial substances. Studies
344 report that microbial counts increase with OMW quantities and frequency of spreading [125,138]. In
345 particular, aerobic bacteria and fungi increase in proportion with OMW spreading rates.
346 Furthermore, soil respiration [101,104] and soil enzyme activities (dehydrogenase, β -glucosidase and
347 urease) seem to be enhanced in OMW-amended soils [128,129].

348 A study on short and long-term effects of repeated OMWW applications [106] showed a
349 temporary negative effect on microbial biomass carbon but also the ability of soil to restore normal
350 values in the long term; moreover, on treated soils, despite a reduction of arbuscular mycorrhiza
351 fungal root colonization, an increased presence of arbuscules and vesicles was observed.

352 - **Growth and yield of crops:** Almost always positive responses on plant growth and yield
353 performances are reported when treated OMW (by composting or co-composting) are used as a
354 consequence of polyphenols biodegradation; however, fertilizations or irrigations with untreated
355 OMW at high doses can harm seeds germination and have negative effects on plant growth due to
356 the phytotoxic effects of the elevated load of polyphenols and high salinity. Recent articles concerning
357 the effect of OMW on plant growth and yield performances are listed in Table 2.

358 **Table 2.** Recent studies on the effects of OMWs on plants growth and yield.

Plant organism	OMW		Plant growth performance		Notes	References
	OMWW	OP	Positive	Negative		

	Raw	Treated	Raw	Treated			
Italian ryegrass		*		*	Germination index	[139]	
Olive trees			POC from MPD	POC from MPD	Long-term field study	[116]	
Maize	*			*	Field trials calcareous soil	[126]	
Durum wheat	*			*	Field trials	[108]	
Barley						[110]	
Olive trees	*			*	Long-term field study	[125]	
Olive trees	*			*	Long-term field study	[140]	
Faba bean	*			dose 25 m ³ /ha	Pot trials with different doses	[102]	
Olive trees	*			Olive grove yield	Long-term field study	[128]	
Grapevine	*			*	Long-term field study (11 years)	[104]	
Olive plantlets			*	*	pot trials in greenhouse	[141]	
Winter Weath	*	*		(OMWW treated)	(OMWW raw)	Field trials	[129]

359

360 5.3. Effects of OMW as biopesticides in plant protection

361 In the agronomic industry a huge problem is represented by fungal and bacterial pathogens that
 362 cause significant crops losses and produce mycotoxins potentially harmful for human health.

363 Plant diseases are largely addressed using synthetic pesticides that have a negative impact on
 364 environment contamination, are harmful to health and can also generate pest-resistance. Bio-
 365 pesticides have been recently described as the best candidates for the control of phytopathogens for
 366 a sustainable agriculture.

367 The application of OMWs by-products in crop protection against pests takes advantage of their
 368 antifungal and antimicrobial properties without negative effects on plant growth [142,143].

369 Several experimental evidences reported the fungicidal activity of OMWW against dangerous
370 phytopathogens.

371 Inhibitory activity of OMWW on *in vitro* mycelium growth of *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Pythium*
372 *spp.*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Verticillium dahlia* and *Botrytis cinerea* was reported [144,145]. Strong
373 fungicidal activity of water extracts of WPO, diluted 1:10, was demonstrated against *Phytophthora*
374 *capsica* [146]. Filter sterilized OMWW also inhibited the *in vitro* mycelium growth of *B. tulipae*, *F.*
375 *oxysporum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium spp* [147].

376 Furthermore, OMWW fruit application strongly reduced *B. cinerea* mold formation in
377 strawberries and red peppers, indicating a possible application of this by-product in fruit
378 protection against post-harvest diseases [145].

379 OMW sterilization abolished all these biological effects suggesting that the antifungal and
380 protective effect on fruits and vegetables from post-harvest diseases were possibly due to
381 thermolabile phenolic compounds, although a synergistic effect of phenols with other molecules
382 could not be excluded.

383 Increased accumulation of phenolic phytoalexins in plants can promote host defense against
384 pathogens and the activity of phenols in plant defense against phytopathogens have been explored
385 for their application as biopesticides in agriculture [148].

386 Due to their low solubility in oil phase, only 2% of phenols are contained in olive oil. Phenols
387 mainly occur in OP (~45%) and in OMWW (~53%) [142] by-products making these wastes an
388 important source of these molecules [143].

389 Caffeic acid, protocatechuic acid, para-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, cinnamic acid and oleuropein
390 isolated from OP, at a concentration of 1000 ppm, exhibited fungicidal activity against numerous
391 phytopathogens with higher effect on *F. oxysporum* and *Verticillium sp* [149]. A powerful fungicidal
392 effect of phenols extracted from DOP at a concentration of 0.1 and 0.2% (w/v) was also demonstrated
393 against *Alternaria solani*, *F. culmorum*, *Phytophthora capsici* and *B. cinerea* (Winkelhausen et al., 2005).

394 Evidences indicated that the antifungal effect of OMWW is related to low molecular weight
395 phenols and in particular to hydroxytyrosol (HT) and tyrosol. OMWW and HT-rich extracts inhibited
396 the growth of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv tomato and *Xanthomonas campestris* at concentrations of 72
397 and 40 g/L, respectively [151]. Interestingly, OMWW at a minimum quantity of 10 µL/mL added to
398 the medium inhibited the *in vitro* growth of the devastating bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*. Moreover a
399 bacteriostatic effect was exerted by specific mono and polyphenols associated with OWS such as
400 catechol and methyl catechol (1mM), caffeic acid (1mM), oleuropein (10mM) and verbascoside (1mM)
401 [152]. However, the mechanism for *X. fastidiosa* growth inhibition by phenols is still unknown
402 [153,154].

403 To understand the molecular basis of HT antifungal activity, different chemically synthesized
404 HT analogues were used against *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *F. oxysporum* and mycelial growth. HT
405 analogues altered plasma membrane structure within some minutes after their addition to fungal
406 cultures. The HT analogues effect was associated to the inhibition of transporter mediated xanthine
407 uptake, indicating that the direct effect of HT analogues was the disruption of the fungal plasma
408 membrane integrity and function [155].

409 Plant cell wall (CW) is a source of bioactive molecules [156]. Cell wall fragments, so called
410 damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), released after enzymatic degradation of CW
411 polysaccharides can improve plant protection as well as crop yield [157].

412 OMWW is a good source of polysaccharides. Cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectins are the main
413 carbohydrates identified in olive mill by-products [5]. While insoluble cellulose and hemicelluloses
414 were mainly found in OP, soluble pectic components were observed in OMWW at significant
415 concentrations [71,158–160]. Long (polymerization degree DP:10-15) and short pectin fragments
416 (DP:1-8) (oligogalacturonides; OGs) are the best characterized DAMPs and are effective as protectors
417 against phytopathogens [161–163]. These danger signals have shown to trigger the CW-mediated
418 immunity system leading to the elicitation of defense responses and disease resistance as well as they
419 can improve crop yield. Peculiar OGs with prebiotic and antioxidant activity have been fractionated
420 from OMWs [65,164–166].

421 Acidic xylooligosaccharides are antimicrobial active agents [167,168], neutral xyloglucans act
 422 as endogenous elicitors [168] and arabinoxylan oligosaccharides can trigger plant immune responses
 423 in crops [69]. OGs neutral and acidic xyloglucan oligosaccharides have been detected in olive fruits
 424 [158–160] and have been isolated and chemically characterized from WOP [84]. Although the role of
 425 these olive oligosaccharides in plant defense has not yet been explored, future research could reveal
 426 their potential properties as new DAMPs to be used in plant protection.

427 Recent articles concerning the effect of OMWs and derived bioactive molecules on
 428 phytopathogens are listed in Table 3.

429 **Table 3.** Recent studies on the effects of OMWs and derived molecules on microbial
 430 phytopathogens.

Microbial organism	Tested sample	Notes	References
<i>Botrytis tulipae</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Penicillium spp</i>	OMWW	Reduction of <i>in vitro</i> mycelium growth Reduction of Scab-like lesions <i>B. tulipae</i> on infected tulip bulbs	[147]
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	OMWW and OMWs-derived MF, UF and NF fractions.	Inhibition of <i>in vitro</i> bacterium growth at minimum quantity of 10 µL/mL	[152]
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	Hydroxytyrosol analogues	Severe inhibition of myceliar growth at 100 µM	[155]
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Cathecol, Methyl cathecol, Caffeic acid, Verbascoside and Oleuperin	Inhibition activity due to a bacteriostatic effect of tested phenols at 1mM and 10mM	[152]

431 It is known that microbial communities have the ability to colonize OMWs and OMW microbiota
 432 depends on different physico-chemical conditions of OMWs as well by the cultivation systems, the
 433 olive tree cultivar and olive fruit harvesting practices [169]. The potential biotechnological and
 434 industrial applications of indigenous microbiota, isolated from OMWs, in suppressive properties
 435 against plant pathogens and OMW bioremediation and valorization are beyond the aims of this
 436 review. However, it is important to highlight that OWM microbiota could modify the pH of the olive
 437 waste substrates and the composition of bioactive molecules during OMW conservation period thus
 438 affecting their efficiency as biopesticide in plant protection. Consequently, in the analyses of the
 439 biological effects of the OMW-derived bioactive molecules the effect of a possible microbial
 440 colonization by indigenous microorganisms needs to be considered and a strict control of the storage
 441 and working conditions is highly required to correctly manage these wastes.

443

444 6. Conclusions and future perspectives

445 While OMW have been for a long time an environmental issue, nowadays they are a source of
 446 bioactive molecules to be used in agriculture as natural pesticides, biostimulants or plant protectants
 447 in alternative to harmful agrochemicals. New types of wastes, in particular POC, must be thoroughly
 448 studied to identify all potentially useful components, such as oligosaccharides to be employed as
 449 plant protectants, as well as phenols and secoiridoids with potential antimicrobial properties. The
 450 definition of molecular mechanisms of action, coupling and complementing protection activity of
 451 phenol and carbohydrate fractions could represent an attractive scientific challenge. In particular,
 452 basic research in plant biology may benefit from the isolation and characterization of new
 453 biomolecules to be potentially applied in crop growth and protection against diseases.

454 Researches on OMW as fertilizers have demonstrated two different potential uses: as
 455 biostimulants or as soil amendments. The phenolic contents in OMW composition, at adequate

456 concentrations, is able to determine positive metabolic and physiological responses in plants. In
457 addition to phenols, attention should be devoted to olive oligosaccharides for their potential role as
458 elicitors of defense responses. Their characterization and effects as plant elicitors of defense responses
459 have not yet been investigated.

460 There are few studies aimed to investigate the specific and/or synergistic actions of phenols and
461 oligosaccharides in the complexity of the soil-plant system; further and more focused researches in
462 these topics are need as a challenge in the valorization of Olive Mill by-products in formulations
463 complying to the new EU biostimulants regulations and towards a sustainable agriculture.

464 OMW effectiveness against phytopathogens has already been investigated and confirmed in
465 many scientific experiences although their recovery with green approaches and their possible use in
466 field applications still need to be further explored. A step in this direction is the ABASA project
467 (Agricultural By-products into valuable Assets for Sustainable Agriculture) recently founded by
468 LazioInnova- Regione Lazio 2017-2020, which has the aim to characterize the phytochemical
469 composition of POC and OMWW fractionated by membrane filtration technologies, as well as to
470 isolate and assess the physiological role of bioactive molecules.

471 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization, DB, AM, DP, CP, UN, AB; writing-original draft preparation, FS, LC,
472 VL, RA, SS, CF, LG, BB, EF, AB, AM, UN, DP, CP, DB; writing—review and editing, FS, LC, CP, DP, AB, UN,
473 AM, DB; supervision, CP, DB. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

474 **Funding:** “This research was funded by Lazio Innova-Regione Lazio, "Progetti di gruppi di ricerca - Conoscenza
475 e cooperazione per un nuovo modello di sviluppo" ABASA grant number 85-2017-15080 CUP:
476 B81G18000770002”.

477 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

478 References

- 479 1. Olive oil Available online: [https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/plants-](https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/plants-and-plant-products/plant-products/olive-oil_en)
480 [and-plant-products/plant-products/olive-oil_en](https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/plants-and-plant-products/plant-products/olive-oil_en) (accessed on Oct 29, 2020).
- 481 2. Khdair, A.; Abu-Rumman, G. Sustainable Environmental Management and
482 Valorization Options for Olive Mill Byproducts in the Middle East and North Africa
483 (MENA) Region. *Processes* **2020**, *8*, 671, doi:10.3390/pr8060671.
- 484 3. Souilem, S.; El-Abbassi, A.; Kiai, H.; Hafidi, A.; Sayadi, S.; Galanakis, C.M. Olive
485 oil production sector: environmental effects and sustainability challenges. In *Olive*
486 *Mill Waste*; Elsevier, 2017; pp. 1–28 ISBN 978-0-12-805314-0.
- 487 4. Dermeche, S.; Nadour, M.; Larroche, C.; Moulti-Mati, F.; Michaud, P. Olive mill
488 wastes: Biochemical characterizations and valorization strategies. *Process*
489 *Biochemistry* **2013**, *48*, 1532–1552, doi:10.1016/j.procbio.2013.07.010.
- 490 5. Nadour, M.; Laroche, C.; Pierre, G.; Delattre, C.; Moulti-Mati, F.; Michaud, P.
491 Structural Characterization and Biological Activities of Polysaccharides from Olive
492 Mill Wastewater. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol* **2015**, *177*, 431–445, doi:10.1007/s12010-
493 015-1753-5.
- 494 6. Aggoun, M.; Arhab, R.; Cornu, A.; Portelli, J.; Barkat, M.; Graulet, B. Olive mill
495 wastewater microconstituents composition according to olive variety and extraction
496 process. *Food Chemistry* **2016**, *209*, 72–80, doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.04.034.
- 497 7. Ochando-Pulido, J.M.; Pimentel-Moral, S.; Verardo, V.; Martinez-Ferez, A. A focus
498 on advanced physico-chemical processes for olive mill wastewater treatment.
499 *Separation and Purification Technology* **2017**, *179*, 161–174,
500 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2017.02.004.

- 501 8. Velásquez, A.C.; Castroverde, C.D.M.; He, S.Y. Plant and pathogen warfare under
502 changing climate conditions. *Curr Biol* **2018**, *28*, R619–R634,
503 doi:10.1016/j.cub.2018.03.054.
- 504 9. Drobek, M.; Fraç, M.; Cybulska, J. Plant Biostimulants: Importance of the Quality and
505 Yield of Horticultural Crops and the Improvement of Plant Tolerance to Abiotic
506 Stress—A Review. *Agronomy* **2019**, *9*, 335, doi:10.3390/agronomy9060335.
- 507 10. Ogunnupebi, T.A.; Oluyori, A.P.; Dada, A.O.; Oladeji, O.S.; Inyinbor, A.A.;
508 Egharevba, G.O. Promising Natural Products in Crop Protection and Food
509 Preservation: Basis, Advances, and Future Prospects. *International Journal of*
510 *Agronomy* **2020**, *2020*, 1–28, doi:10.1155/2020/8840046.
- 511 11. Coppola, A.; Renzo, G.C.D.; Altieri, G.; D'Antonio, P. *Innovative Biosystems*
512 *Engineering for Sustainable Agriculture, Forestry and Food Production:*
513 *International Mid-Term Conference 2019 of the Italian Association of Agricultural*
514 *Engineering (AIIA)*; Springer Nature, 2020; ISBN 978-3-030-39299-4.
- 515 12. Sygouni, V.; Pantziaros, A.G.; Iakovides, I.C.; Sfetsa, E.; Bogdou, P.I.; Christoforou,
516 E.A.; Paraskeva, C.A. Treatment of Two-Phase Olive Mill Wastewater and Recovery
517 of Phenolic Compounds Using Membrane Technology. *Membranes (Basel)* **2019**, *9*,
518 doi:10.3390/membranes9020027.
- 519 13. Lozano-Sánchez, J.; Bendini, A.; Lecce, G.D.; Valli, E.; Toschi, T.G.; Segura-
520 Carretero, A. Macro and micro functional components of a spreadable olive by-
521 product (pâté) generated by new concept of two-phase decanter. *European Journal of*
522 *Lipid Science and Technology* **2017**, *119*, 1600096, doi:10.1002/ejlt.201600096.
- 523 14. Antónia Nunes, M.; Costa, A.S.G.; Bessada, S.; Santos, J.; Puga, H.; Alves, R.C.;
524 Freitas, V.; Oliveira, M.B.P.P. Olive pomace as a valuable source of bioactive
525 compounds: A study regarding its lipid- and water-soluble components. *Science of The*
526 *Total Environment* **2018**, *644*, 229–236, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.350.
- 527 15. Cecchi, L.; Bellumori, M.; Cipriani, C.; Mocali, A.; Innocenti, M.; Mulinacci, N.;
528 Giovannelli, L. A two-phase olive mill by-product (pâté) as a convenient source of
529 phenolic compounds: Content, stability, and antiaging properties in cultured human
530 fibroblasts. *Journal of Functional Foods* **2018**, *40*, 751–759,
531 doi:10.1016/j.jff.2017.12.018.
- 532 16. Tufariello, M.; Durante, M.; Veneziani, G.; Taticchi, A.; Servili, M.; Bleve, G.; Mita,
533 G. Patè Olive Cake: Possible Exploitation of a By-Product for Food Applications.
534 *Front Nutr* **2019**, *6*, doi:10.3389/fnut.2019.00003.
- 535 17. Tundis, R.; Conidi, C.; Loizzo, M.R.; Sicari, V.; Cassano, A. Olive Mill Wastewater
536 Polyphenol-Enriched Fractions by Integrated Membrane Process: A Promising Source
537 of Antioxidant, Hypolipidemic and Hypoglycaemic Compounds. *Antioxidants* **2020**,
538 *9*, 602, doi:10.3390/antiox9070602.
- 539 18. Belaid, C.; Khadraoui, M.; Mseddi, S.; Kallel, M.; Elleuch, B.; Fauvarque, J.F.
540 Electrochemical treatment of olive mill wastewater: Treatment extent and effluent
541 phenolic compounds monitoring using some uncommon analytical tools. *Journal of*
542 *Environmental Sciences* **2013**, *25*, 220–230, doi:10.1016/S1001-0742(12)60037-0.

- 543 19. Christoforou, E.; Kylili, A.; Fokaides, P.A. Technical and economical evaluation of
544 olive mills solid waste pellets. *Renewable Energy* **2016**, *96*, 33–41,
545 doi:10.1016/j.renene.2016.04.046.
- 546 20. Moharram, H.; Youssef, M. Methods for Determining the Antioxidant Activity: A
547 Review. *Alex. J. Fd. Sci. & Technol.* **2014**, *11*, 31–42.
- 548 21. Pisoschi, A.M.; Negulescu, G.P. Methods for Total Antioxidant Activity
549 Determination: A Review. *Biochem & Anal Biochem* **2012**, *01*, doi:10.4172/2161-
550 1009.1000106.
- 551 22. Antolovich, M.; Prenzler, P.D.; Patsalides, E.; McDonald, S.; Robards, K. Methods
552 for testing antioxidant activity. *Analyst* **2002**, *127*, 183–198, doi:10.1039/B009171P.
- 553 23. Opitz, S.; Smrke, S.; Goodman, B.A.; Yeretzyan, C. Methodology for the measurement
554 of antioxidant capacity of coffee: a validated platform composed of three
555 complementary antioxidant assays. *Processing and impact on antioxidants in*
556 *beverage* **2014**, 253–264, doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-404738-9.00026-X.
- 557 24. Pisoschi, A.M.; Cheregi, M.C.; Danet, A.F. Total antioxidant capacity of some
558 commercial fruit juices: electrochemical and spectrophotometrical approaches.
559 *Molecules* **2009**, *14*, 480–493, doi:10.3390/molecules14010480.
- 560 25. Ordoudi, S.A.; Tsimidou, M.Z. Crocin bleaching assay (CBA) in structure-radical
561 scavenging activity studies of selected phenolic compounds. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*
562 **2006**, *54*, 9347–9356, doi:10.1021/jf062115d.
- 563 26. Finotti, E.; Bersani, A.M.; Bersani, E. Total Quality Indexes for Extra-Virgin Olive
564 Oils. *Journal of Food Quality* **2007**, *30*, 911–931, doi:10.1111/j.1745-
565 4557.2007.00159.x.
- 566 27. Amir, S.; Hafidi, M.; Merlina, G.; Hamdi, H.; Revel, J.-C. Elemental analysis, FTIR
567 and ¹³C-NMR of humic acids from sewage sludge composting. *Agronomie* **2004**, *24*,
568 13–18, doi:10.1051/agro:2003054.
- 569 28. Hafidi, M.; Amir, S.; Revel, J.-C. Structural characterization of olive mill waster-water
570 after aerobic digestion using elemental analysis, FTIR and ¹³C NMR. *Process*
571 *Biochemistry* **2005**, *40*, 2615–2622, doi:10.1016/j.procbio.2004.06.062.
- 572 29. Obied, H.K.; Karuso, P.; Prenzler, P.D.; Robards, K. Novel secoiridoids with
573 antioxidant activity from Australian olive mill waste. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2007**, *55*,
574 2848–2853, doi:10.1021/jf063300u.
- 575 30. El Hajjouji, H.; Merlina, G.; Pinelli, E.; Winterton, P.; Revel, J.-C.; Hafidi, M. ¹³C
576 NMR study of the effect of aerobic treatment of olive mill wastewater (OMW) on its
577 lipid-free content. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2008**, *154*, 927–932,
578 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.10.105.
- 579 31. Sannino, F.; De Martino, A.; Capasso, R.; El Hadrami, I. Valorisation of organic
580 matter in olive mill wastewaters: Recovery of highly pure hydroxytyrosol. *Journal of*
581 *Geochemical Exploration* **2013**, *129*, 34–39, doi:10.1016/j.gexplo.2012.10.009.
- 582 32. Zghari, B.; Doumenq, P.; Romane, A.; Boukir, A. GC-MS, FTIR and ¹H, ¹³C NMR
583 Structural Analysis and Identification of Phenolic Compounds in Olive Mill
584 Wastewater Extracted from Oued Oussefrou Effluent (Beni Mellal-Morocco). *JMES*
585 **2017**, *8*, 4496–4509, doi:10.26872/jmes.2017.8.12.475.

- 586 33. Ait Baddi, G.; Hafidi, M.; Cegarra, J.; Albuquerque, J.A.; González, J.; Gilard, V.;
587 Revel, J.-C. Characterization of fulvic acids by elemental and spectroscopic (FTIR and
588 ¹³C-NMR) analyses during composting of olive mill wastes plus straw. *Bioresour.*
589 *Technol.* **2004**, *93*, 285–290, doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2003.10.026.
- 590 34. Ntougias, S.; Gaitis, F.; Katsaris, P.; Skoulika, S.; Iliopoulos, N.; Zervakis, G.I. The
591 effects of olives harvest period and production year on olive mill wastewater properties
592 – Evaluation of *Pleurotus* strains as bioindicators of the effluent's toxicity.
593 *Chemosphere* **2013**, *92*, 399–405, doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.01.033.
- 594 35. Uribe, E.; Pasten, A.; Lemus-Mondaca, R.; Vega-Gálvez, A.; Quispe-Fuentes, I.;
595 Ortiz, J.; Scala, K.D. Comparison of Chemical Composition, Bioactive Compounds
596 and Antioxidant Activity of Three Olive-Waste Cakes. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*
597 **2015**, *39*, 189–198, doi:10.1111/jfbc.12120.
- 598 36. Gullón, P.; Gullón, B.; Astray, G.; Carpena, M.; Fraga-Corral, M.; Prieto, M.A.;
599 Simal-Gandara, J. Valorization of by-products from olive oil industry and added-value
600 applications for innovative functional foods. *Food Research International* **2020**, *137*,
601 109683, doi:10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109683.
- 602 37. Cecchi, L.; Bellumori, M.; Cipriani, C.; Mocali, A.; Innocenti, M.; Mulinacci, N.;
603 Giovannelli, L. A two-phase olive mill by-product (pâte) as a convenient source of
604 phenolic compounds: Content, stability, and antiaging properties in cultured human
605 fibroblasts. *Journal of Functional Foods* **2018**, *40*, 751–759,
606 doi:10.1016/j.jff.2017.12.018.
- 607 38. Mateos, R.; Espartero, J.L.; Trujillo, M.; Ríos, J.J.; León-Camacho, M.; Alcludia, F.;
608 Cert, A. Determination of Phenols, Flavones, and Lignans in Virgin Olive Oils by
609 Solid-Phase Extraction and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography with Diode
610 Array Ultraviolet Detection. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2001**, *49*, 2185–2192,
611 doi:10.1021/jf0013205.
- 612 39. Zafra Gomez, A.; Luzón-Toro, B.; Capel-Cuevas, S.; Morales, J. Stability of
613 Hydroxytyrosol in Aqueous Solutions at Different Concentration, Temperature and
614 with Different Ionic Content: A Study Using UPLC-MS. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*
615 **2011**, *2*, 1114–1120, doi:10.4236/fns.2011.210149.
- 616 40. Boutaj, H.; Boutasknit, A.; Anli, M.; Ait Ahmed, M.; El Abbassi, A.; Meddich, A.
617 Insecticidal Effect of Olive Mill Wastewaters on *Potosia opaca* (Coleoptera:
618 Scarabeidae) Larva. *Waste and Biomass Valorization* **2020**, *11*, 3397–3405,
619 doi:10.1007/s12649-019-00682-1.
- 620 41. Ventura, G.; Calvano, C.D.; Abbattista, R.; Bianco, M.; De Ceglie, C.; Losito, I.;
621 Palmisano, F.; Cataldi, T.R.I. Characterization of bioactive and nutraceutical
622 compounds occurring in olive oil processing wastes. *Rapid Communications in Mass*
623 *Spectrometry* **2019**, *33*, 1670–1681, doi:10.1002/rcm.8514.
- 624 42. Jiménez-Herrera, S.; Ochando-Pulido, J.M.; Martínez-Ferez, A. Comparison between
625 different liquid-liquid and solid phase methods of extraction prior to the identification
626 of the Phenolic fraction present in olive oil washing wastewater from the two-phase
627 olive oil extraction system. *Grasas y Aceites* **2017**, *68*, doi:10.3989/gya.0225171.

- 628 43. Zghari, B.; Doumenq, P.; Romane, A.; Boukir, A. GC-MS, FTIR and ^1H , ^{13}C NMR
629 Structural Analysis and Identification of Phenolic Compounds in Olive Mill
630 Wastewater Extracted from Oued Oussefrou Effluent (Beni Mellal-Morocco). *JMES*
631 **2017**, *8*, 4496–4509, doi:10.26872/jmes.2017.8.12.475.
- 632 44. Silvan, J.M.; Pinto-Bustillos, M.A.; Vázquez-Ponce, P.; Prodanov, M.; Martinez-
633 Rodriguez, A.J. Olive mill wastewater as a potential source of antibacterial and anti-
634 inflammatory compounds against the food-borne pathogen *Campylobacter*. *Innovative*
635 *Food Science & Emerging Technologies* **2019**, *51*, 177–185,
636 doi:10.1016/j.ifset.2018.05.013.
- 637 45. Antónia Nunes, M.; Costa, A.S.G.; Bessada, S.; Santos, J.; Puga, H.; Alves, R.C.;
638 Freitas, V.; Oliveira, M.B.P.P. Olive pomace as a valuable source of bioactive
639 compounds: A study regarding its lipid- and water-soluble components. *Science of The*
640 *Total Environment* **2018**, *644*, 229–236, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.350.
- 641 46. Friedman, M.; Levin, C.E.; Henika, P.R. Addition of phytochemical-rich plant extracts
642 mitigate the antimicrobial activity of essential oil/wine mixtures against *Escherichia*
643 *coli* O157:H7 but not against *Salmonella enterica*. *Food Control* **2017**, *73*, 562–565,
644 doi:10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.09.002.
- 645 47. De Marco, E.; Savarese, M.; Paduano, A.; Sacchi, R. Characterization and
646 fractionation of phenolic compounds extracted from olive oil mill wastewaters. *Food*
647 *Chemistry* **2007**, *104*, 858–867, doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.10.005.
- 648 48. Soler-Rivas, C.; Espín, J.C.; Wichers, H.J. Oleuropein and related compounds. *Journal*
649 *of the Science of Food and Agriculture* **2000**, *80*, 1013–1023, doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-
650 0010(20000515)80:7<1013::AID-JSFA571>3.0.CO;2-C.
- 651 49. Obied, H.K.; Allen, M.S.; Bedgood, D.R.; Prenzler, P.D.; Robards, K.; Stockmann, R.
652 Bioactivity and Analysis of Biophenols Recovered from Olive Mill Waste. *J. Agric.*
653 *Food Chem.* **2005**, *53*, 823–837, doi:10.1021/jf048569x.
- 654 50. Silvan, J.M.; Pinto-Bustillos, M.A.; Vázquez-Ponce, P.; Prodanov, M.; Martinez-
655 Rodriguez, A.J. Olive mill wastewater as a potential source of antibacterial and anti-
656 inflammatory compounds against the food-borne pathogen *Campylobacter*. *Innovative*
657 *Food Science & Emerging Technologies* **2019**, *51*, 177–185,
658 doi:10.1016/j.ifset.2018.05.013.
- 659 51. Cardoso, S.M.; Falcão, S.I.; Peres, A.M.; Domingues, M.R.M. Oleuropein/ligstroside
660 isomers and their derivatives in Portuguese olive mill wastewaters. *Food Chemistry*
661 **2011**, *129*, 291–296, doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.04.049.
- 662 52. Ghisalberti, E.L. Biological and pharmacological activity of naturally occurring
663 iridoids and secoiridoids. *Phytomedicine* **1998**, *5*, 147–163, doi:10.1016/S0944-
664 7113(98)80012-3.
- 665 53. Araújo, M.; Pimentel, F.B.; Alves, R.C.; Oliveira, M.B.P.P. Phenolic compounds from
666 olive mill wastes: Health effects, analytical approach and application as food
667 antioxidants. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **2015**, *45*, 200–211,
668 doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2015.06.010.

- 669 54. Liu, Y.; McKeever, L.C.; Malik, N.S.A. Assessment of the Antimicrobial Activity of
670 Olive Leaf Extract Against Foodborne Bacterial Pathogens. *Front Microbiol* **2017**, *8*,
671 doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.00113.
- 672 55. Castro, M.; Japón-Luján, R. State-of-the-art and trends in the analysis of oleuropein
673 and derivatives. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry* **2006**, *25*, 501–510,
674 doi:10.1016/j.trac.2005.11.007.
- 675 56. Miranda, I.; Simões, R.; Medeiros, B.; Nampoothiri, K.M.; Sukumaran, R.K.; Rajan,
676 D.; Pereira, H.; Ferreira-Dias, S. Valorization of lignocellulosic residues from the olive
677 oil industry by production of lignin, glucose and functional sugars. *Bioresour Technol*
678 **2019**, *292*, 121936, doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2019.121936.
- 679 57. Jiménez, A.; Guillén, R.; Fernández-Bolaños, J.; Heredia, A. Cell Wall Composition
680 of Olives. *Journal of Food Science* **1994**, *59*, 1192–1196, doi:10.1111/j.1365-
681 2621.1994.tb14674.x.
- 682 58. Mafra, I.; Lanza, B.; Reis, A.; Marsilio, V.; Campestre, C.; Angelis, M.D.; Coimbra,
683 M. Effect of ripening on texture, microstructure and cell wall polysaccharide
684 composition of olive fruit (*Olea europaea*). *Physiologia plantarum* **2001**,
685 doi:10.1034/J.1399-3054.2001.1110403.X.
- 686 59. Jiménez, A.; Rodríguez, R.; Fernández-Caro, I.; Guillén, R.; Fernández-Bolaños, J.;
687 Heredia, A. Olive Fruit Cell Wall: Degradation of Pectic Polysaccharides during
688 Ripening. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2001**, *49*, 409–415, doi:10.1021/jf000235u.
- 689 60. Huisman, M.M.H.; Schols, H.A.; Voragen, A.G.J. Changes in cell wall
690 polysaccharides from ripening olive fruits. *Carbohydrate Polymers* **1996**, *31*, 123–
691 133, doi:10.1016/S0144-8617(96)00069-0.
- 692 61. Cardoso, S.M.; Coimbra, M.A.; Lopes da Silva, J.A. Calcium-mediated gelation of an
693 olive pomace pectic extract. *Carbohydrate Polymers* **2003**, *52*, 125–133,
694 doi:10.1016/S0144-8617(02)00299-0.
- 695 62. Vierhuis, E.; Korver, M.; Schols, H.A.; Voragen, A.G.J. Structural characteristics of
696 pectic polysaccharides from olive fruit (*Olea europaea* cv *moraiolo*) in relation to
697 processing for oil extraction. *Carbohydrate Polymers* **2003**, *51*, 135–148,
698 doi:10.1016/S0144-8617(02)00158-3.
- 699 63. Galanakis, C.M. Separation of functional macromolecules and micromolecules: From
700 ultrafiltration to the border of nanofiltration. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*
701 **2015**, *42*, 44–63, doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2014.11.005.
- 702 64. Galanakis, C.M.; Tornberg, E.; Gekas, V. A study of the recovery of the dietary fibres
703 from olive mill wastewater and the gelling ability of the soluble fibre fraction. *Food*
704 *Science and Technology* **2010**, *43*, 1009–1017, doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2010.01.005.
- 705 65. Cano, M.E.; García-Martin, A.; Comendador Morales, P.; Wojtusik, M.; Santos, V.E.;
706 Kovensky, J.; Ladero, M. Production of Oligosaccharides from Agrofood Wastes.
707 *Fermentation* **2020**, *6*, 31, doi:10.3390/fermentation6010031.
- 708 66. Suárez, L.; Savatin, D.V.; Salvi, G.; Lorenzo, G.D.; Cervone, F.; Ferrari, S. The non-
709 traditional growth regulator Pectomorfin is an elicitor of defense responses and protects
710 *Arabidopsis* against *Botrytis cinerea*. *Journal of Plant Pathology* **2013**, *95*, 177–180,
711 doi:10.4454/JPP.V95I1.021.

- 712 67. Souza, C. de A.; Li, S.; Lin, A.Z.; Boutrot, F.; Grossmann, G.; Zipfel, C.; Somerville,
713 S.C. Cellulose-Derived Oligomers Act as Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns and
714 Trigger Defense-Like Responses. *Plant Physiol.* **2017**, *173*, 2383–2398,
715 doi:10.1104/pp.16.01680.
- 716 68. De Lorenzo, G.; Ferrari, S.; Cervone, F.; Okun, E. Extracellular DAMPs in Plants and
717 Mammals: Immunity, Tissue Damage and Repair. *Trends in Immunology* **2018**, *39*,
718 937–950, doi:10.1016/j.it.2018.09.006.
- 719 69. Mérida, H.; Bacete, L.; Ruprecht, C.; Rebaque, D.; del Hierro, I.; López, G.; Brunner,
720 F.; Pfrengle, F.; Molina, A. Arabinoxylan-Oligosaccharides Act as Damage
721 Associated Molecular Patterns in Plants Regulating Disease Resistance Available
722 online: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpls.2020.01210/full> (accessed
723 on Oct 15, 2020).
- 724 70. Roberfroid, M.; Slavin, J. Nondigestible oligosaccharides. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*
725 **2000**, *40*, 461–480, doi:10.1080/10408690091189239.
- 726 71. Galanakis, C.M.; Tornberg, E.; Gekas, V. Dietary fiber suspensions from olive mill
727 wastewater as potential fat replacements in meatballs. *LWT - Food Science and*
728 *Technology* **2010**, *43*, 1018–1025, doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2009.09.011.
- 729 72. Dermeche, S.; Nadour, M.; Larroche, C.; Moulti-Mati, F.; Michaud, P. Olive mill
730 wastes: Biochemical characterizations and valorization strategies. *Process*
731 *Biochemistry* **2013**, *48*, 1532–1552, doi:10.1016/j.procbio.2013.07.010.
- 732 73. Reem, N.; Pogorelko, G.; Lionetti, V.; Chambers, L.; Held, M.A.; Bellincampi, D.;
733 Zobotina, O.A. Decreased polysaccharide feruloylation compromises plant cell wall
734 integrity and increases susceptibility to necrotrophic fungal pathogens. *Front.Plant*
735 *Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 630, doi: 10.3389/fpls.2016.00630.
- 736 74. Guillén, R.; Heredia, A.; Felizón, B.; Jiménez, A.; Montañón, A.; Fernández-Bolaños,
737 J. Fibre fraction carbohydrates in *Olea europaea* (Gordal and Manzanilla var.). *Food*
738 *Chemistry* **1992**, *44*, 173–178, doi:10.1016/0308-8146(92)90183-3.
- 739 75. Alonso, S.; Setser, C. Functional replacements for sugars in foods. *Trends in Food*
740 *Science & Technology* **1994**, *5*, 139–146, doi:10.1016/0924-2244(94)90119-8.
- 741 76. Stoop, J.; Williamson, J.; Masonpharr, D. Mannitol metabolism in plants: a method
742 for coping with stress. *Trends in Plant Science* **1996**, *1*, 139–144, doi:10.1016/S1360-
743 1385(96)80048-3.
- 744 77. Tholalabavi, A.; Zwiazek, J.J.; Thorpe, T.A. Effect of mannitol and glucose-induced
745 osmotic stress on growth, water relations, and solute composition of cell suspension
746 cultures of poplar (*Populus deltoides* var. *Occidentalis*) in relation to anthocyanin
747 accumulation. *In Vitro Cell Dev Biol - Plant* **1994**, *30*, 164–170,
748 doi:10.1007/BF02632208.
- 749 78. Capasso, R.; de Martino, A.; Arienzo, M. Recovery and Characterization of the Metal
750 Polymeric Organic Fraction (Polymerin) from Olive Oil Mill Wastewaters. *J. Agric.*
751 *Food Chem.* **2002**, *50*, 2846–2855, doi:10.1021/jf011442c.
- 752 79. Capasso, R.; Pigna, M.; De Martino, A.; Pucci, M.; Sannino, F.; Violante, A. Potential
753 Remediation of Waters Contaminated with Cr(III), Cu, and Zn by Sorption on the

- 754 Organic Polymeric Fraction of Olive Mill Wastewater (Polymerin) and Its Derivatives.
755 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2004**, *38*, 5170–5176, doi:10.1021/es0400234.
- 756 80. Bazinet, L.; Doyen, A. Antioxidants, mechanisms, and recovery by membrane
757 processes. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* **2017**, *57*, 677–700,
758 doi:10.1080/10408398.2014.912609.
- 759 81. El-Abbassi, A.; Hafidi, A.; Khayet, M.; Garc á-Payo, M.C. Integrated direct contact
760 membrane distillation for olive mill wastewater treatment. *Desalination* **2013**, *323*,
761 31–38, doi:10.1016/j.desal.2012.06.014.
- 762 82. El-Abbassi, A.; Kiai, H.; Raiti, J.; Hafidi, A. Application of ultrafiltration for olive
763 processing wastewaters treatment. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **2014**, *65*, 432–438,
764 doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.08.016.
- 765 83. Galanakis, C.M.; Tornberg, E.; Gekas, V. Clarification of high-added value products
766 from olive mill wastewater. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2010**, *99*, 190–197,
767 doi:10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2010.02.018.
- 768 84. Lama-Muñoz, A.; Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, G.; Rubio-Senent, F.; Fernández-Bolaños, J.
769 Production, characterization and isolation of neutral and pectic oligosaccharides with
770 low molecular weights from olive by-products thermally treated. *Food Hydrocolloids*
771 **2012**, *28*, 92–104, doi:10.1016/j.foodhyd.2011.11.008.
- 772 85. Stoller, M.; Pulido, J.M.O.; Di Palma, L.; Ferez, A.M. Membrane process
773 enhancement of 2-phase and 3-phase olive mill wastewater treatment plants by
774 photocatalysis with magnetic-core titanium dioxide nanoparticles. *Journal of*
775 *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* **2015**, *30*, 147–152,
776 doi:10.1016/j.jiec.2015.05.015.
- 777 86. Rizvi, S.S.H. *Supercritical Fluid Processing of Food and Biomaterials*; Springer US,
778 1994; ISBN 978-1-4613-5907-4.
- 779 87. Baysal, T.; Ersus, S.; Starmans, D.A.J. Supercritical CO₂ Extraction of β-Carotene and
780 Lycopene from Tomato Paste Waste. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2000**, *48*, 5507–5511,
781 doi:10.1021/jf000311t.
- 782 88. D áz-Maroto, M.C.; Pérez-Coello, M.S.; Cabezudo, M.D. Supercritical carbon dioxide
783 extraction of volatiles from spices. Comparison with simultaneous distillation-
784 extraction. *J Chromatogr A* **2002**, *947*, 23–29, doi:10.1016/s0021-9673(01)01585-0.
- 785 89. Şahin, S.; Bilgin, M. Study on Oleuropein Extraction From Olive Tree (*Olea*
786 *europaea*) Leaves by Means of SFE: Comparison of Water and Ethanol as CoSolvent.
787 *Separation Science and Technology* **2012**, *47*, doi:10.1080/01496395.2012.666311.
- 788 90. Markhali, F.S.; Teixeira, J.A.; Rocha, C.M.R. Olive Tree Leaves—A Source of
789 Valuable Active Compounds. *Processes* **2020**, *8*, 1177, doi:10.3390/pr8091177.
- 790 91. Caballero, A.S.; Romero-García, J.M.; Castro, E.; Cardona, C.A. Supercritical fluid
791 extraction for enhancing polyphenolic compounds production from olive waste
792 extracts. *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology* **2020**, *95*, 356–362,
793 doi:10.1002/jctb.5907.
- 794 92. Schievano, A.; Adani, F.; Buessing, L.; Botto, A.; Casoliba, E.N.; Rossoni, M.;
795 Goldfarb, J.L. An integrated biorefinery concept for olive mill waste management:

- 796 supercritical CO₂ extraction and energy recovery. *Green Chem.* **2015**, *17*, 2874–2887,
797 doi:10.1039/c5gc00076a.
- 798 93. Regulation (EU) 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019
799 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products
800 and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing
801 Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003. 114.
- 802 94. Ricci, M.; Tilbury, L.; Daridon, B.; Sukalac, K. General Principles to Justify Plant
803 Biostimulant Claims. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2019**, *10*, doi:10.3389/fpls.2019.00494.
- 804 95. Roupheal, Y.; Colla, G. Editorial: Biostimulants in Agriculture. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2020**,
805 *11*, 40, doi:10.3389/fpls.2020.00040.
- 806 96. Palumbo, G.; Schiavon, M.; Nardi, S.; Ertani, A.; Celano, G.; Colombo, C.M.
807 Biostimulant Potential of Humic Acids Extracted From an Amendment Obtained via
808 Combination of Olive Mill Wastewaters (OMW) and a Pre-treated Organic Material
809 Derived From Municipal Solid Waste (MSW). *Front. Plant Sci.* **2018**, *9*, 1028,
810 doi:10.3389/fpls.2018.01028.
- 811 97. Ertani, A.; Francioso, O.; Tinti, A.; Schiavon, M.; Pizzeghello, D.; Nardi, S.
812 Evaluation of Seaweed Extracts From *Laminaria* and *Ascophyllum nodosum* spp. as
813 Biostimulants in *Zea mays* L. Using a Combination of Chemical, Biochemical and
814 Morphological Approaches. *Front Plant Sci* **2018**, *9*, doi:10.3389/fpls.2018.00428.
- 815 98. Leopoldini, M.; Russo, N.; Toscano, M. The molecular basis of working mechanism
816 of natural polyphenolic antioxidants. *Food Chemistry* **2011**, *125*, 288–306,
817 doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.08.012.
- 818 99. Garc á-S áchez, M.; Garrido, I.; Casimiro, I. de J.; Casero, P.J.; Espinosa, F.; Garc á-
819 Romera, I.; Aranda, E. Defence response of tomato seedlings to oxidative stress
820 induced by phenolic compounds from dry olive mill residue. *Chemosphere* **2012**, *89*,
821 708–716, doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2012.06.026.
- 822 100. Killi, D.; Kavdır, Y. Effects of olive solid waste and olive solid waste compost
823 application on soil properties and growth of *Solanum lycopersicum*. *International*
824 *Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* **2013**, *82*, 157–165,
825 doi:10.1016/j.ibiod.2013.03.004.
- 826 101. Mekki, A.; Dhouib, A.; Sayadi, S. Changes in microbial and soil properties following
827 amendment with treated and untreated olive mill wastewater. *Microbiological*
828 *Research* **2006**, *161*, 93–101, doi:10.1016/j.micres.2005.06.001.
- 829 102. Sdiri Ghidaoui, J.; Bargougui, L.; Chaieb, M.; Mekki, A. Study of the phytotoxic
830 potential of olive mill wastewaters on a leguminous plant ‘*Vicia faba* L.’ *Water*
831 *Science and Technology* **2019**, *80*, 1295–1303, doi:10.2166/wst.2019.373.
- 832 103. Justino, C.I.L.; Pereira, R.; Freitas, A.C.; Rocha-Santos, T.A.P.; Panteleitchouk,
833 T.S.L.; Duarte, A.C. Olive oil mill wastewaters before and after treatment: a critical
834 review from the ecotoxicological point of view. *Ecotoxicology* **2012**, *21*, 615–629,
835 doi:10.1007/s10646-011-0806-y.
- 836 104. Lanza, B.; Di Serio, M.G.; Di Giovacchino, L. Microbiological and Chemical
837 Modifications of Soil Cultivated with Grapevine Following Agronomic Application of

- 838 Olive Mill Wastewater. *Water Air Soil Pollut* **2020**, *231*, 86, doi:10.1007/s11270-020-
839 4462-9.
- 840 105. Barbera, A.C.; Maucieri, C.; Cavallaro, V.; Ioppolo, A.; Spagna, G. Effects of
841 spreading olive mill wastewater on soil properties and crops, a review. *Agricultural*
842 *Water Management* **2013**, *119*, 43–53, doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2012.12.009.
- 843 106. Di Bene, C.; Pellegrino, E.; Debolini, M.; Silvestri, N.; Bonari, E. Short- and long-
844 term effects of olive mill wastewater land spreading on soil chemical and biological
845 properties. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **2013**, *56*, 21–30,
846 doi:10.1016/j.soilbio.2012.02.019.
- 847 107. Rusan, M.J.M.; Albalasmeh, A.A.; Zuraiqi, S.; Bashabsheh, M. Evaluation of
848 phytotoxicity effect of olive mill wastewater treated by different technologies on seed
849 germination of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Environ Sci Pollut Res* **2015**, *22*, 9127–
850 9135, doi:10.1007/s11356-014-4004-3.
- 851 108. Mohawesh, O.; Al-Hamaiedeh, H.; Albalasmeh, A.; Qaraleh, S.; Haddadin, M. Effect
852 of Olive Mill Wastewater (OMW) Application on Soil Properties and Wheat Growth
853 Performance Under Rain-Fed Conditions. *Water Air Soil Pollut* **2019**, *230*, 160,
854 doi:10.1007/s11270-019-4208-8.
- 855 109. Zema, D.A.; Esteban Lucas-Borja, M.; Andiloro, S.; Tamburino, V.; Zimbone, S.M.
856 Short-term effects of olive mill wastewater application on the hydrological and
857 physico-chemical properties of a loamy soil. *Agricultural Water Management* **2019**,
858 *221*, 312–321, doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2019.04.011.
- 859 110. Mohawesh, O.; Albalasmeh, A.; Al-Hamaiedeh, H.; Qaraleh, S.; Maaitah, O.;
860 Bawalize, A.; Almajali, D. Controlled Land Application of Olive Mill Wastewater
861 (OMW): Enhance Soil Indices and Barley Growth Performance in Arid Environments.
862 *Water Air Soil Pollut* **2020**, *231*, 214, doi:10.1007/s11270-020-04612-z.
- 863 111. Ahmed, P.M.; Fernández, P.M.; Figueroa, L.I.C.; Pajot, H.F. Exploitation alternatives
864 of olive mill wastewater: production of value-added compounds useful for industry
865 and agriculture. *Biofuel Res. J.* **2019**, *6*, 980–994, doi:10.18331/BRJ2019.6.2.4.
- 866 112. Aquilanti, L.; Taccari, M.; Bruglieri, D.; Osimani, A.; Clementi, F.; Comitini, F.;
867 Ciani, M. Integrated biological approaches for olive mill wastewater treatment and
868 agricultural exploitation. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* **2014**, *88*,
869 162–168, doi:10.1016/j.ibiod.2013.12.010.
- 870 113. M. Rusan, M.J.; Albalasmeh, A.A.; Malkawi, H.I. Treated Olive Mill Wastewater
871 Effects on Soil Properties and Plant Growth. *Water Air Soil Pollut* **2016**, *227*, 135,
872 doi:10.1007/s11270-016-2837-8.
- 873 114. Chartzoulakis, K.; Psarras, G.; Moutsopoulou, M.; Stefanoudaki, E. Application of
874 olive mill wastewater to a Cretan olive orchard: Effects on soil properties, plant
875 performance and the environment. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* **2010**, *138*,
876 293–298, doi:10.1016/j.agee.2010.05.014.
- 877 115. Killi, D.; Kavdır, Y. Effects of olive solid waste and olive solid waste compost
878 application on soil properties and growth of *Solanum lycopersicum*. *International*
879 *Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* **2013**, *82*, 157–165,
880 doi:10.1016/j.ibiod.2013.03.004.

- 881 116. Proietti, P.; Federici, E.; Fidati, L.; Scargetta, S.; Massaccesi, L.; Nasini, L.; Regni, L.;
882 Ricci, A.; Cenci, G.; Gigliotti, G. Effects of amendment with oil mill waste and its
883 derived-compost on soil chemical and microbiological characteristics and olive (*Olea*
884 *europaea* L.) productivity. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* **2015**, *207*, 51–60,
885 doi:10.1016/j.agee.2015.03.028.
- 886 117. Rajhi, H.; Mnif, I.; Abichou, M.; Rhouma, A. Assessment and valorization of treated
887 and non-treated olive mill wastewater (OMW) in the dry region. *Int J Recycl Org*
888 *Waste Agricult* **2018**, *7*, 199–210, doi:10.1007/s40093-018-0206-x.
- 889 118. Ameziane, H.; Nounah, A.; Khamar, M.; Zouahri, A. Composting olive pomace:
890 evolution of organic matter and compost quality. **2020**, 663.5Kb,
891 doi:10.15159/AR.20.004.
- 892 119. Ait Baddi, G.; Hafidi, M.; Gilard, V.; Revel, J.-C. Characterization of humic acids
893 produced during composting of olive mill wastes: elemental and spectroscopic
894 analyses (FTIR and ¹³C-NMR). *Agronomie* **2003**, *23*, 661–666,
895 doi:10.1051/agro:2003042.
- 896 120. Aviani, I.; Laor, Y.; Medina, Sh.; Krassnovsky, A.; Raviv, M. Co-composting of solid
897 and liquid olive mill wastes: Management aspects and the horticultural value of the
898 resulting composts. *Bioresource Technology* **2010**, *101*, 6699–6706,
899 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2010.03.096.
- 900 121. Gigliotti, G.; Proietti, P.; Said-Pullicino, D.; Nasini, L.; Pezzolla, D.; Rosati, L.;
901 Porceddu, P.R. Co-composting of olive husks with high moisture contents: Organic
902 matter dynamics and compost quality. *International Biodeterioration &*
903 *Biodegradation* **2012**, *67*, 8–14, doi:10.1016/j.ibiod.2011.11.009.
- 904 122. Bargougui, L.; Chaieb, M.; Mekki, A. Monitoring Cocomposting of Agro-Wastes
905 from Olive Mill By-Products and Poultry Manures. *Environmental Engineering*
906 *Science* **2020**, ees.2020.0136, doi:10.1089/ees.2020.0136.
- 907 123. Alburquerque, J. Agrochemical characterisation of “alperujo”, a solid by-product of
908 the two-phase centrifugation method for olive oil extraction. *Bioresource Technology*
909 **2004**, *91*, 195–200, doi:10.1016/S0960-8524(03)00177-9.
- 910 124. Fernández-Hernández, A.; Roig, A.; Serramiá N.; Civantos, C.G.-O.; Sánchez-
911 Monedero, M.A. Application of compost of two-phase olive mill waste on olive grove:
912 Effects on soil, olive fruit and olive oil quality. *Waste Management* **2014**, *34*, 1139–
913 1147, doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2014.03.027.
- 914 125. Ayoub, S.; Al-Absi, K.; Al-Shdiefat, S.; Al-Majali, D.; Hijazeen, D. Effect of olive
915 mill wastewater land-spreading on soil properties, olive tree performance and oil
916 quality. *Scientia Horticulturae* **2014**, *175*, 160–166,
917 doi:10.1016/j.scienta.2014.06.013.
- 918 126. Belaqziz, M.; El-Abbassi, A.; Lakhel, E.K.; Agrafioti, E.; Galanakis, C.M. Agronomic
919 application of olive mill wastewater: Effects on maize production and soil properties.
920 *Journal of Environmental Management* **2016**, *171*, 158–165,
921 doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.02.006.

- 922 127. Chaari, L.; Elloumi, N.; Mseddi, S.; Gargouri, K.; Rouina, B.B.; Mechichi, T.; Kallel,
923 M. Changes in Soil Macronutrients after a Long-Term Application of Olive Mill
924 Wastewater. *JACEN* **2015**, *04*, 1–13, doi:10.4236/jacen.2015.41001.
- 925 128. Magdich, S.; Rouina, B.B.; Ammar, E. Olive Mill Wastewater Agronomic
926 Valorization by its Spreading in Olive Grove. *Waste and Biomass Valorization* **2020**,
927 *11*, 1359–1372, doi:10.1007/s12649-018-0471-y.
- 928 129. Okur, N.; Kayıkçıoğlu, H.H.; Okur, B.; Yağmur, B.; Sponza Teresa, D.; Kara, R.S. A
929 study of olive mill wastewaters obtained from different treatment processes effects on
930 chemical and microbial properties of a typic xerofluent soil and wheat yield. *Turkish*
931 *Journal of Agriculture and Forestry* **2020**, *44*, 140–155, doi:10.3906/tar-1902-75.
- 932 130. Mohawesh, O.; Albalasmeh, A.A.; Qaraleh, S. Effect of Olive Mill Wastewater
933 (OMW) Application on Soil Properties and Wheat Growth Performance Under Rain-
934 Fed Conditions. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*.
- 935 131. Lozano-García, B.; Parras-Alcántara, L.; del Toro Carrillo de Albornoz, M. Effects of
936 oil mill wastes on surface soil properties, runoff and soil losses in traditional olive
937 groves in southern Spain. *CATENA* **2011**, *85*, 187–193,
938 doi:10.1016/j.catena.2011.01.017.
- 939 132. Nektarios, P.A.; Ntoulas, N.; McElroy, S.; Volterrani, M.; Arbis, G. Effect of Olive
940 Mill Compost on Native Soil Characteristics and Tall Fescue Turfgrass Development.
941 *Agronomy Journal* **2011**, *103*, 1524–1531, doi:10.2134/agronj2011.0145.
- 942 133. Abu-Rumman, G. Effect of Olive Mill Solid Waste on Soil Physical Properties.
943 *International J. of Soil Science* **2016**, *11*, 94–101, doi:10.3923/ijss.2016.94.101.
- 944 134. Mahmoud, M.; Janssen, M.; Peth, S.; Horn, R.; Lennartz, B. Long-term impact of
945 irrigation with olive mill wastewater on aggregate properties in the top soil. *Soil and*
946 *Tillage Research* **2012**, *124*, 24–31, doi:10.1016/j.still.2012.04.002.
- 947 135. Mohawesh, O.; Mahmoud, M.; Janssen, M.; Lennartz, B. Effect of irrigation with olive
948 mill wastewater on soil hydraulic and solute transport properties. *Int. J. Environ. Sci.*
949 *Technol.* **2014**, *11*, 927–934, doi:10.1007/s13762-013-0285-1.
- 950 136. Albalasmeh, A.A.; Alajlouni, M.A.; Ghariabeh, M.A.; Rusan, M.J. Short-Term Effects
951 of Olive Mill Wastewater Land Spreading on Soil Physical and Hydraulic Properties.
952 *Water Air Soil Pollut* **2019**, *230*, 208, doi:10.1007/s11270-019-4243-5.
- 953 137. Cabrera, D.; López-Piñero, A.; Albarrán, Á.; Peñá, D. Direct and residual effects on
954 diuron behaviour and persistence following two-phase olive mill waste addition to soil:
955 Field and laboratory experiments. *Geoderma* **2010**, *157*, 133–141,
956 doi:10.1016/j.geoderma.2010.04.004.
- 957 138. Magdich, S.; Ben Ahmed, C.; Jarbou, R.; Ben Rouina, B.; Boukhris, M.; Ammar, E.
958 Dose and frequency dependent effects of olive mill wastewater treatment on the
959 chemical and microbial properties of soil. *Chemosphere* **2013**, *93*, 1896–1903,
960 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.06.066.
- 961 139. Cavallaro, V.; Maucieri, C.; Barbera, A.C. *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. cvs germination
962 under simulated olive mill wastewater salinity and pH stress. *Ecological Engineering*
963 **2014**, *71*, 113–117, doi:10.1016/j.ecoleng.2014.07.055.

- 964 140. Montemurro, F.; Ferri, D.; Fiore, A.; Diacono, M. Suitability of Untreated and
965 Composted Olive Mill By-Products as Amendments in Organic Olive Orchards.
966 *Compost Science & Utilization* **2014**, *22*, 216–229,
967 doi:10.1080/1065657X.2014.930676.
- 968 141. Endeshaw, S.T.; Lodolini, E.M.; Neri, D. Effects of untreated two-phase olive mill
969 pomace on potted olive plantlets. *Ann Appl Biol* **2015**, *166*, 508–519,
970 doi:10.1111/aab.12200.
- 971 142. El-Abbassi, A.; Saadaoui, N.; Kiai, H.; Raiti, J.; Hafidi, A. Potential applications of
972 olive mill wastewater as biopesticide for crops protection. *Science of The Total*
973 *Environment* **2017**, *576*, 10–21, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.032.
- 974 143. Panzella, L.; Moccia, F.; Nasti, R.; Marzorati, S.; Verotta, L.; Napolitano, A. Bioactive
975 Phenolic Compounds From Agri-Food Wastes: An Update on Green and Sustainable
976 Extraction Methodologies. *Front. Nutr.* **2020**, *7*, doi:10.3389/fnut.2020.00060.
- 977 144. Vagelas, I.; Kalorizou, H.; Papachatzis, A.; Botu, M. Bioactivity of Olive Oil Mill
978 Wastewater Against Plant Pathogens and Post-Harvest Diseases. *Biotechnology &*
979 *Biotechnological Equipment* **2009**, *23*, 1217–1219,
980 doi:10.1080/13102818.2009.10817641.
- 981 145. Vagelas, I.; Papachatzis, A.; Kalorizou, H.; Wogiatzi, E. Biological Control of *Botrytis*
982 Fruit Rot (Gray Mold) on Strawberry and Red Pepper Fruits by Olive Oil Mill
983 Wastewater. *Biotechnology & Biotechnological Equipment* **2009**, *23*, 1489–1491,
984 doi:10.2478/V10133-009-0017-3.
- 985 146. Cayuela, M.L.; Millner, P.D.; Meyer, S.L.F.; Roig, A. Potential of olive mill waste
986 and compost as biobased pesticides against weeds, fungi, and nematodes. *Science of*
987 *The Total Environment* **2008**, *399*, 11–18, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2008.03.031.
- 988 147. Lykas, C.; Vagelas, I.; Gougoulas, N. Effect of olive mill wastewater on growth and
989 bulb production of tulip plants infected by bulb diseases. *Span J Agric Res* **2014**, *12*,
990 233, doi:10.5424/sjar/2014121-4662.
- 991 148. Daayf, F.; Hadrami, A.E.; El-Bebany, A.F.; Henriquez, M.A.; Yao, Z.; Derksen, H.;
992 El-Hadrami, I.; Adam, L.R. Phenolic Compounds in Plant Defense and Pathogen
993 Counter-Defense Mechanisms. In *Recent Advances in Polyphenol Research*; John
994 Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2012; pp. 191–208 ISBN 978-1-118-29975-3.
- 995 149. Al-Mughrabi, K.I.; Aburjai, T.A.; Anfoka, G.H.; Shahrour, W. Antifungal activity of
996 olive cake extracts. *Phytopathologia Mediterranea* **2001**, *40*, 240–244.
- 997 150. Winkelhausen, E.; Pospiech, R.; Laufenberg, G. Antifungal activity of phenolic
998 compounds extracted from dried olive pomace. **2005**.
- 999 151. Yangui, T.; Sayadi, S.; Dhouib, A. Sensitivity of *Pectobacterium carotovorum* to
1000 hydroxytyrosol-rich extracts and their effect on the development of soft rot in potato
1001 tubers during storage. *Crop Protection* **2013**, *53*, 52–57,
1002 doi:10.1016/j.cropro.2013.06.014.
- 1003 152. Bleve, G.; Gallo, A.; Altomare, C.; Vurro, M.; Maiorano, G.; Cardinali, A.;
1004 D'Antuono, I.; Marchi, G.; Mita, G. In vitro activity of antimicrobial compounds
1005 against *Xylella fastidiosa*, the causal agent of the olive quick decline syndrome in
1006 Apulia (Italy). *FEMS Microbiol Lett* **2018**, *365*, doi:10.1093/femsle/fnx281.

- 1007 153. Thielmann, J.; Kohnen, S.; Hauser, C. Antimicrobial activity of *Olea europaea* Linn é
1008 extracts and their applicability as natural food preservative agents. *International*
1009 *Journal of Food Microbiology* **2017**, *251*, 48–66,
1010 doi:10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2017.03.019.
- 1011 154. Robles-Almazan, M.; Pulido-Moran, M.; Moreno-Fernandez, J.; Ramirez-Tortosa, C.;
1012 Rodriguez-Garcia, C.; Quiles, J.L.; Ramirez-Tortosa, Mc. Hydroxytyrosol:
1013 Bioavailability, toxicity, and clinical applications. *Food Research International* **2018**,
1014 *105*, 654–667, doi:10.1016/j.foodres.2017.11.053.
- 1015 155. Diallinas, G.; Rafailidou, N.; Kalpaktsi, I.; Komianou, A.C.; Tsouvali, V.; Zantza, I.;
1016 Mikros, E.; Skaltsounis, A.L.; Kostakis, I.K. Hydroxytyrosol (HT) Analogs Act as
1017 Potent Antifungals by Direct Disruption of the Fungal Cell Membrane. *Front.*
1018 *Microbiol.* **2018**, *9*, 2624, doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.02624.
- 1019 156. Bellincampi, D.; Cervone, F.; Lionetti, V. Plant cell wall dynamics and wall-related
1020 susceptibility in plant-pathogen interactions. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2014**, *5*,
1021 doi:10.3389/fpls.2014.00228.
- 1022 157. Hou, S.; Liu, Z.; Shen, H.; Wu, D. Damage-Associated Molecular Pattern-Triggered
1023 Immunity in Plants. *Front Plant Sci* **2019**, *10*, doi:10.3389/fpls.2019.00646.
- 1024 158. Vierhuis, E.; Schols, H.A.; Beldman, G.; Voragen, A.G.J. Structural characterisation
1025 of xyloglucan and xylans present in olive fruit (*Olea europaea* cv *koroneiki*).
1026 *Carbohydrate Polymers* **2001**, *44*, 51–62, doi:10.1016/S0144-8617(00)00199-5.
- 1027 159. Vierhuis, E.; York, W.S.; Kolli, V.S.; Vincken, J.; Schols, H.A.; Van Alebeek, G.W.;
1028 Voragen, A.G. Structural analyses of two arabinose containing oligosaccharides
1029 derived from olive fruit xyloglucan: XXSG and XLSG. *Carbohydr Res* **2001**, *332*,
1030 285–297, doi:10.1016/s0008-6215(01)00096-9.
- 1031 160. Vierhuis, E.; Korver, M.; Schols, H.A.; Voragen, A.G.J. Structural characteristics of
1032 pectic polysaccharides from olive fruit (*Olea europaea* cv *moraiolo*) in relation to
1033 processing for oil extraction. *Carbohydrate Polymers* **2003**, *51*, 135–148,
1034 doi:10.1016/S0144-8617(02)00158-3.
- 1035 161. Ferrari, S. Oligogalacturonides: plant damage-associated molecular patterns and
1036 regulators of growth and development. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2013**, *4*,
1037 doi:10.3389/fpls.2013.00049.
- 1038 162. Davidsson, P.; Broberg, M.; Kariola, T.; Sipari, N.; Pirhonen, M.; Palva, E.T. Short
1039 oligogalacturonides induce pathogen resistance-associated gene expression in
1040 *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *BMC Plant Biol* **2017**, *17*, 19, doi:10.1186/s12870-016-0959-1.
- 1041 163. Escudero, V.; Jord á L.; Sope ña-Torres, S.; Méida, H.; Miedes, E.; Muñoz-Barrios,
1042 A.; Swami, S.; Alexander, D.; McKee, L.S.; Sánchez-Vallet, A.; et al. Alteration of
1043 cell wall xylan acetylation triggers defense responses that counterbalance the immune
1044 deficiencies of plants impaired in the β -subunit of the heterotrimeric G-protein. *Plant*
1045 *J* **2017**, *92*, 386–399, doi:10.1111/tpj.13660.
- 1046 164. Coimbra, M.A.; Cardoso, S.M.; Lopes-da-Silva, J.A. Olive Pomace, a Source for
1047 Valuable Arabinan-Rich Pectic Polysaccharides. In *Carbohydrates in Sustainable*
1048 *Development I*; Rauter, A.P., Vogel, P., Queneau, Y., Eds.; Topics in Current

- 1049 Chemistry; Springer: Berlin, Heidelberg, 2010; pp. 129–141 ISBN 978-3-642-14837-
1050 8.
- 1051 165. Babbar, N.; Dejonghe, W.; Gatti, M.; Sforza, S.; Elst, K. Pectic oligosaccharides from
1052 agricultural by-products: production, characterization and health benefits. *Critical*
1053 *Reviews in Biotechnology* **2015**, 1–13, doi:10.3109/07388551.2014.996732.
- 1054 166. Nadour, M.; Laroche, C.; Pierre, G.; Delattre, C.; Moulti-Mati, F.; Michaud, P.
1055 Structural Characterization and Biological Activities of Polysaccharides from Olive
1056 Mill Wastewater. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol* **2015**, 177, 431–445, doi:10.1007/s12010-
1057 015-1753-5.
- 1058 167. Christakopoulos, P.; Katapodis, P.; Kalogeris, E.; Kekos, D.; Macris, B.J.; Stamatis,
1059 H.; Skaltsa, H. Antimicrobial activity of acidic xylo-oligosaccharides produced by
1060 family 10 and 11 endoxylanases. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*
1061 **2003**, 31, 171–175, doi:10.1016/S0141-8130(02)00079-X.
- 1062 168. Claverie, J.; Balacey, S.; Lemaître-Guillier, C.; Brulé D.; Chiltz, A.; Granet, L.;
1063 Noirot, E.; Daire, X.; Darblade, B.; Hédoir, M.-C.; et al. The Cell Wall-Derived
1064 Xyloglucan Is a New DAMP Triggering Plant Immunity in *Vitis vinifera* and
1065 *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2018**, 9, doi:10.3389/fpls.2018.01725.
- 1066 169. Ntougias, S.; Bourtzis, K.; Tsiamis, G. The Microbiology of Olive Mill Wastes.
1067 *BioMed research international* **2013**, 2013, 784591, doi:10.1155/2013/784591.
1068

© 2020 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).